

Degree of Applicability of Blended Learning Modality in Reading and Writing Skills

Ian Paul P. Campos¹, Hanylen M. Fernandez²

¹Researcher, Graduate School, Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception, Baybay City, Leyte, Philippines

²Faculty, Graduate School, Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception, Baybay City, Leyte, Philippines

Corresponding Author's Email: iancampos@fcic.edu.ph

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the applicability of blended learning modality in reading and writing at Dolores National High School, Ormoc City. It identifies the socio- demographic profile of students, the Reading and Writing Performance Level of the students, the degree of applicability of blended learning in developing their English language skills and aims to present the significant difference between the socio- demographic profile and the degree of applicability of blended learning modality in reading and writing. The study selected its respondents using a simple random sampling technique, and statistical treatments such as frequency, percentage, and Chi-square were used. The majority of the respondents were 14 to 15 years old, with a mean reading skill level of 90.705 interpreted as Instructional. The writing performance level, on the other hand, had a mean of 89.9496 described as Acceptable, The Degree of Applicability of Blended Learning in Developing the Students' English Language Skills in Terms of Reading obtained an average mean of 3.28 (Applicable), and the "Degree of Applicability of Blended Learning in Developing the Students' English Language Skills in Terms of Writing" obtained an average mean of 3.29 (Applicable), indicating that the indicators listed were all applicable.

Keywords: *reading, writing, degree of applicability, skills, performance*

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INTRODUCTION

The pandemic drastically brought changes in the world and in the educational system around the globe. When schools shut down at the start of the pandemic and with the gradual implementation of the limited face-to-face classes, educators and the whole educational system were challenged in coping with the demands of sustaining quality education through distance learning. As a result, the modular, online, and blended learning approaches become the learning modalities implemented – modified and enhanced as suited to the level of learners, their learning environment, and their living conditions at home with their parents and guardians being their home learning partners as described by Bordoloi et.al (2020).

As the country continued to face various challenges caused by the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic in 2020, the Department of Education (DepEd) issued DepEd Order No. 012, s.2020 that supports the Adoption of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) for the School Year 2020-2021 in light of the COVID-19 Public Health Emergency. The BE-LCP provides the development of educational interventions in response to the challenges in continuing education amidst the public health emergency brought on by COVID-19. Through DepEd’s vision and mission, teachers and school administrators, as the front liners, collaboratively work on strategies to deliver learning and operate its services together with the full support of both the internal and external stakeholders.

This continuity of learning and operational services is aimed to be carried out effectively while ensuring the safety, health, and well-being of students, teachers, and school and office personnel under the Department of Education. Further, it protects and promotes the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels strengthening the educational mandate under Article 14(1) of the 1987 Constitution to provide an access to quality education for all. It stipulates the legal basis of how the country takes appropriate measures consistent with its mandate that include identifying ways to continue education during the crisis brought on by the pandemic. In particular, the BE-LCP, as Thompson (2018) endorses, should respond to the “new normal” while respecting its constitutional obligation to defend the rights of all citizens to quality education at all times.

Among the new normal modalities strategized by some schools in the Department of Education, as part of the BE-LCP, is Blended Learning that is a combination of face-to-face instruction with any or a combination of modular distance learning, online distance learning, and television/radio-based instruction is facilitated. In continuing learning amidst the pandemic, blended learning aims to provide the best face- to-face and online as well as modular/home-based learning experiences for students. As reiterated by Ferlazzo (2020), blended learning is part of how schools redesigned their teaching-learning modality when faced with the threats of COVID-19. Specifically, it covers learning instructions facilitated face-to-face such as direct instruction or lecture, group discussions, and small-group work with the use of technology to provide in-class online learning that students can do at home provided they have access to necessary technology. More to say, it has become not just an educational trend but as well as the “new normal” and alternative learning modality.

In the Philippine educational setting, under the Department of Education, blended learning has been around even before the pandemic strikes. It is a part of the Alternative

Delivery Mode (ADM) in the Philippines accommodating adult learners and secondary-level students as presented by Villanueva (2021). However, this growing demand for blended learning possesses problems and challenges that are noteworthy to investigate as contended by Alvarez (2020). First, in the list of challenges, is the learners' ability to learn independently without structured and regular support from teachers same as with the face- to-face and from parents or guardians as their home learning partners compromising the overall development of students as they have limited or no interactions with their teachers, as learning facilitators as well as from their classmates. Second, the mass production of learning materials needed by teachers and learners and the support of media institutions such as television and radio stations also play a decisive role in its implementation. Third, DepEd requires significantly additional financial resources to meet its BE-LCP goals aligned with blended learning and other learning modalities viable during the time of the pandemic. In addition, adding up to these challenges is the effect of blended learning on the development of learners' core communication skills such as reading and writing.

The development of reading skills includes both vocabulary and text comprehension as well as the higher- order thinking skills that it taps. For reading to be extensively developed, the active process of comprehension should include word recognition, sentence processing, strategic processing, relevant background knowledge activation, meaning interpretation, and constant monitoring of one's reading comprehension as explicated by Grabe (2014). These extensive reading processes are efficiently practiced with the usual face- to-face learning interactions but still with deficiencies. Same as true for how it poses a challenge for bridging these active reading processes in Blended learning. It is rooted in the conventions that face-to-face learning interactions provided with scaffolding intensified the development of communication skills such as reading. Arancon, Barcena, and Arus (2012) support this challenge as active interactions and scaffolding from teachers to learners and learners to peers are an advantage in conventional face-to-face learning and a disadvantage in blended learning. Moreover, as cited by de Vera (2020) from the United Children's Fund (UNICEF) report, there is less than 15% of Filipino school children, particularly equating to about three out of 20 school children, can read simple texts in large part as a result of the prolonged school closure and distance learning facilitated due to COVID-19. Added to this is the more than 85% of Filipino school children aged 10 who cannot read a simple story that translates the learning poverty in the Philippines according to the World Bank compared to the 69.5% learning poverty rate report in 2019. This reading deficiency is also evident in the locale of the study, in Dolores National High School, with only 2.5% of independent readers from the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil- IRI) report of the school as of June 2022. This indicates that a larger percentage of readers are classified in the instructional (developing) level and some are still in the frustration level.

Another communication skill is the writing skills that is equally important as the reading skills. As defined by Kaplan (2023), writing skills involve components such as research, planning, outlining, spelling, grammar, revising, and organization. This is among the skill, together with reading, that is targeted to be developed despite the challenges of bridging the gap that distance learning brings. Merga et.al (2021) present the impact of COVID-19 and distance learning to the development of learners' writing skills as perceived by teachers. It further revealed that the collaborative response from educators and the education system was disrupted leading to developing impediments in learners' writing skills highlighting parental support and technological resources as the needs being challenged with the facilitation of

blended learning. Likewise in the Philippine setting, online learning, a significant part of blended learning, poses a challenge in the development of writing skills based from how Filipino teachers assessed the skill development of their learners. As according to Tarrayo et.al (2022), problems in technological and equity issues, school's unclear responses to remote teaching, and facilitation of effective assessment challenge how teachers teach and develop their learners' writing skills. This is also true as with Dolores National High School, as the locale of the study, with writing skills crucially becoming difficult for students as evaluated from their writing task performances during the facilitation of blended learning. With the challenges in learning, reading and writing skills development associated with the facilitation of blended learning worldwide, in the Philippines and local school setting, the researcher was moved to equate students' performance on the degree of applicability of blended learning in receiving lesson contents in English that develop their reading and writing skills among Grade 9 students of Dolores National High School, Ormoc City.

The instructional effectiveness of teaching English using the blended learning approach is becoming a necessity in the "new normal" during the pandemic and even in the post-pandemic. Thus, this study, specifically benefited the English teachers as they will be well-informed on effective methods and strategies as they deliver their instruction to students, especially those that develop essential English language skills: Reading and Writing with the use of blended learning as an alternative learning modality. It is part of the goal of this study to equip English teachers with methods and strategies to effectively facilitate blended learning in facilitating the development of communication skills through the English lessons. Second, the School Heads, can be able to examine and analyze the teaching difficulties encountered by both students and teachers that affect the level of learning in blended learning. In this regard, they can be able to suggest plans of action or give necessary activities targeted to enrich teachers' capability in delivering their instructions with blended learning as the new normal and alternative delivery mode. Third, the students become recipients of effective instructional methodologies that can enhance their English competence and skills for an increased academic performance with the new teaching-learning pedagogies brought about by blended learning. Fourth, the parents are encouraged to actively participate and support the needs of their children and to closely monitor their child's performance with the new learning modalities implemented. Fifth, the researcher of the study develops meaningful and worthwhile strategies and methodologies considering students' perceptions and performance as they develop English language skills with blended learning as the modality. Lastly, for the future researchers who will be moved to combat issues and concerns regarding instructional efficacy in teaching English with the use of blended learning.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the degree of applicability of blended learning modality in developing reading and writing skills of the Grade 9 students at Dolores National High School, Ormoc City.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of sex, age, and socio-economic status?
2. What is the reading and writing skills performance level of the respondents?

3. What is the degree of applicability of blended learning in developing the reading and writing skills of the respondents?
4. Is there a significant difference in the degree of applicability of blended learning modality among different socio-demographic profiles, and reading and writing skills performance level of the respondents?
5. What can be proposed based on the result of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used a descriptive quantitative method to gather information and to identify the Degree of Applicability of Blended Learning Modality in Reading and Writing Skills. In addition, the descriptive quantitative method was utilized to describe data and characteristics about the population, or the phenomenon being studied. This method also seems to be the most appropriate method to determine the significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and the Degree of Applicability of Blended Learning Modality in Reading and Writing Skills. Lastly, the researcher used a self-constructed questionnaire as a data-gathering instrument to secure information needed for the study. According to Stamoulis (2018), the descriptive research design aimed to measure a relationship between two or more variables. The goal of descriptive-correlational methods of research was to identify predictive relationships by using correlations or more sophisticated statistical techniques. This was likely the case as with the design of the study.

The Sample and Locale of the Study

The respondents of the study were the selected Grade 9 students at Dolores National High School, Ormoc, City. They were selected using simple random sampling. This sampling method of selecting the respondents of the study was seen as effective and attainable considering the locale where the study was conducted. Using random sampling, a sample of 139 respondents were selected from the 204 total number of Grade 9 students enrolled in Dolores National High School. This sampling technique was supported by Bermudo et.al (2020) with the preference of simple random sampling as a technique because it is fast, inexpensive, and easy as the subjects were readily available within the locale where the researcher also teaches as an English teacher.

This study was conducted in Dolores National High School located in Brgy. Dolores, Ormoc City, District 8 which has a total population of 1138 students for the school year 2021-2022. The faculty and staff of the school consist of 46 teachers, Two Administrative Assistants, One Head Teacher, One Master Teacher, and a School Principal. There is a total of 25 advisory classrooms, Five sections from Grade 7 to 9 and four sections in Grade 10 for the Junior High School. For the Senior High School, a total of six sections with three sections per grade level.

The respondents were Grade 9 students and were selected as they had been engaged in developing English language skills in their whole course in English as integrated into the Most

Essential Learning Competencies (MELC) in English Grade 9. They were also selected as to their learning experiences with blended learning adopted in Dolores National High School, Ormoc City, Leyte

Research Instrument

A survey questionnaire was used as the main instrument of the study to determine the degree of applicability of blended learning modality in reading and writing skills. The said survey questionnaire was a researcher-made instrument that was constructed after considering the anchored theory of the study as well as the rich or abundant literature and previous research related to the present study. The instrument used in this study followed the construction, validation, and administration phases of the questionnaire. The instrument used in gathering the data in this study was the questionnaire which was modified and constructed by the researcher and was validated by the research adviser and with the chosen experts in the field of research and statistics, the Statistician of the research study. The preliminary draft of the questionnaire was presented to the thesis adviser for corrections and revisions. All the corrections were incorporated in the finalization of the questionnaire. The questionnaire consisted of three parts. The first part focused on the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, and economic status. The second part was about the “Reading and Writing Skills Performance Level” of the respondents. This was the assessment given to the respondents by the researcher. The researcher prepared and administered an examination that assessed the skills and performance of the respondents in the field of reading and writing.

For the reading assessment, the researcher utilized the Phil-IRI, which refers to the revised assessment tool composed of a set of graded passages administered to the whole class and to individual students, which was designed to determine a student’s reading level. For the writing assessment, student writing was evaluated on five product factors: fluency, content, conventions, syntax, and vocabulary. Writing skills were also assessed across a variety of purposes for writing to give a complete picture of a student's writing performance across different text structures and genres. Then, the third part counted the indicators of the Degree of Applicability of Blended Learning in Reading and Writing Skills. A researcher-made questionnaire was constructed and validated to measure the said variable. The instrument used in this study followed the construction, validation, and administration phases of the questionnaire. The instrument used in gathering the data in this study was the questionnaire which was modified and constructed by the researcher and was validated by the research adviser and with the chosen experts in the field of research and statistics, the Statistician of the research study.

Data Gathering and Analysis

The researcher asked permission from the Dean of the Graduate School, the Schools Division Superintendent, Respondents, and to the School Principal to allow him to formally conduct the study. After the approval of the request to conduct the study and after the survey questionnaire has been validated by some experts in the field, the copies of the questionnaire were distributed personally by the researcher. A span of one hour was given to the respondents in answering the questionnaire for the purpose of obtaining valid and reliable results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The socio-demographic profile of the respondents pertained to their age, sex, and economic/income status. Demographic information allowed us to better understand certain background characteristics of the respondents. Table 2 shows the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, and economic/income status.

Table 2. Socio-Demographic Profile of the Respondents

INDICATORS	CATEGORY	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
	12-13 yrs. old	0	0.0
	14-15 yrs. old	132	95.0
AGE	16-17 yrs. old	7	5.0
	18 yrs. Old	0	0.0
	TOTAL	139	100.0
	MALE	48	34.5
GENDER	FEMALE	91	65.5
	TOTAL	139	100.0
	Php 21,000 and above	85	61.2
SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS	Php 15,000 - Php 20,000	46	33.1
	Php 6,000 - Php 10,000	5	3.6
	below Php 5,000	3	2.2
	TOTAL	139	100.0

Table 2 shows the Age, Sex, and Socio-Economic Status of the Grade 9 students as respondents of the study. In terms of Age, results show the normal age bracket and a few of the students have ages suited for the next Grade level which is Grade 10. It also presented that the majority of the respondents age is from 14-15 years old which has a percentage of 95% of the total responses. This means that the majority of the Grade 9 students belongs to the bracket of that age. This indicates that more of the respondents belong to the school age bracket for Grade 9 for this study and only a few belongs to the upper bracket which could be read that they were more responsible for their studies and needs a little support from teachers and other aspects as stated in the theoretical framework.

The students' age and the degree of applicability of blended learning as applicable supports to the idea that students, coming to this age, had high competence and confidence in using learning tools other than the conventional face-to-face learning interactions that include

technological tools as supported in a study by Kintu, Zhu, & Kagambe (2017). Their age would also help them master self-regulation which is a significant factor in the effectiveness of blended learning, as to how they regarded it as applicable to the development of their reading and writing skills. However, this result is opposed to the findings of Hassanbeigi et al. (2011) wherein senior students show better academic performance compared to junior students in the effectiveness of the applicability of blended learning. It holds true the fact that students have varying degrees of uniqueness as to how they see and work well with things like how they manage well and navigate through the processes of blended learning regardless of their age differences if they find the learning tools suited to their level of needs, aptitudes, and interests. After all, their attitudes and self-regulation are the keys to finding applicable learning experiences in blended learning as supported by Kintu et.al (2017).

As regards to Sex, the Table shows a total percentage of 65.5% for the 91 female respondents compare to 34.5% of the 48 male respondents. Majority of the respondents are female which justifies the findings. The above data were correlated to the idea that a gender perspective to understanding the blended learning approach helped to focus attention on the distinct gender-specific capacities and vulnerabilities to prepare, confront, and follow blended learning practices. Blended learning influenced and helped men and women, and boys and girls, differently. On the contrary, a larger mean of females selected as compared to men selected for this study is a result of the simple random sampling technique used rather than purposive sampling. Furthermore, Adas and Abu Samais (2011) report no significant differences in terms of gender even though the highest means were in favor of the females; however, it was presented that there is a strong significance in students' attitudes toward e-learning, as part of blended learning, between genders. But most studies revealed that the positive attitude of students toward blended learning give a positive impact on its applicability than students' gender differences.

For the Socio-Economic Status, 61.2% of the data from socio-demographic profile belongs to families with Php 21,000 above monthly earnings. This presents that learners who belong to the family with this monthly income can provide all the needs that commensurate to their performance in both reading and writing. Eighty-five had an income of Php 21,000.00 and above which obtained the highest percentage of 61.15%. Below Php 5,000.00 income earners got a frequency of three and a percentage of 2.16%.

When students made the adjustments to the new normal learning delivery mode, the support from their parents was a strong determiner of how well they achieved learning gains during the pandemic. As supported by the study of Li & Qiu (2018), different learning environments provided by parents and families are affected by their economic status, though many parents work on how to make ends meet. They are strong factors in students' successful learning outcomes during the pandemic that included blended learning modality. On the other hand, other researchers have found that most of the Filipino families find it difficult to fully support their children with blended learning, especially those parents who are non-High school graduates and those who are low-income earners. This was also supported in a recent SWS survey (2021) that revealed 89% of Filipino families who preferred to have their children be enrolled in face-to-face learning than in blended learning due to their intellectual capacity to guide their children at home and their income to support technological tools needed in a blended learning set-up.

Reading and Writing Skills Performance Level

Individuals acquired and developed two of the most important skills: reading and writing. Learning these skills contributed to success in everyday life, especially for learners. A solid foundation in reading and writing foster great determination to both teachers and students. As the educational ladder progresses, so do the learner's literacy skills. This emphasized the power of individual basic literacy. Table 3 presents the overall “Reading and Writing Skills Performance Level” of the respondents of the study.

Table 3. Distribution of Reading and Writing Skills Performance Level

INDICATORS	AVERAGE MEAN	DESCRIPTION
Reading	90.705	Instructional
Writing	89.949	Good

Table 3 shows the mean of Reading skills is 90.705 and writing skills is 89.949 in both performance level which falls on Instructional level of Phil-IRI Criteria and Good on Writing assessment. This means that learners in terms of reading and writing comprehension, majority of the participants were considered under the instructional level which means that they would profit from the reading instruction. Although, they are not students who are refusing or withdrawing themselves to read, they can read with assistance. Based on the presented table above, it showed the Overall Performance Skills in Reading and Writing of the respondents.

The foregoing findings and implications lend support to the study of Albrecht (2018) that claimed that blended learning was bringing together Face-to-Face classroom instruction with web-based and other media platforms activities that are engaging, interesting, and interactive for students. In addition, Alpala & Flórez (2018) contends that the use of blended learning makes the students more active in their learning, feeling more technologically empowered, and able to learn anywhere and anytime in the manner that best suits their lifestyle.

Blended learning provides varied learning activities and opportunities that are contextualized easily with the diversity of students as well attributed to their learning environment and multiple intelligences for instance. Thus, it promotes learning motivation such as the motivation to learn and develop their language skills including reading and writing. Hashemi and Kew (2020) reiterated the effectiveness of blended learning because of the diversity and multimodal learning opportunities and experiences provided to students over a single learning delivery mode.

Degree of Applicability of Blended Learning in Reading and Writing Skills

This relates to students' abilities to comprehend, apply, and reflect on written/printed materials to acquire learning competencies as tested by the school's Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI).

Table 4. Degree of Applicability of Blended Learning in Developing the Students' English Language Skills in Terms of Reading

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. My vocabulary increased as I went through the different tasks in blended learning.	3.85	Highly Applicable
2. I gained knowledge on defining words I used in my arguments and ideas.	3.54	Highly Applicable
3. I was able to enhance my phonemic awareness which is the ability to notice, think about, and work with the individual sounds (phonemes) in spoken words.	3.00	Applicable
4. It increases my understanding on how I syllabicate words.	3.49	Applicable
5. I was unable to pronounce words with proper stress.	3.20	Applicable
6. I gained confidence in pronouncing words or groups of words with their appropriate intonation for me to convey meaning properly.	3.10	Applicable
7. I am now aware of how to pronounce words or sentences with their suitable rhythm which enables me to divide speech into words, signals me on every change between topics and spots what ideas on the message are the most important.	3.52	Applicable
8. I learned how to properly pronounce words having consonants and vowel sounds which make my ideas and messages easy to understand.	3.11	Applicable
9. I have also increased my accuracy in pronouncing English words for me to easily share the exact idea to my listeners.	3.25	Applicable
10. I was able to improve my fluency in reading which enables me to quickly span the gap between recognizing a word and understanding its meaning.	3.14	Applicable
11. I have developed my reading comprehension where I can now deeply immerse myself in the reading materials I read.	3.46	Applicable
12. I gained an ever - increasing vocabulary through reading.	3.65	Applicable

13. I enhanced my learning on phonics which taught me to decode letters into their perspective sounds.	3.16	Applicable
14. I improved my phonemic awareness by learning about sounds, syllables and words.	3.12	Applicable
15. I was able to learn how to show that I am listening by using my body language and gestures to convey my attention.	2.50	Applicable
16. I was able to obtain fluency in the way I speak by being comfortable and confident when speaking English.	3.50	Highly Applicable
17. I enhance my speaking skills by having a wide range of vocabulary.	3.47	Applicable
18. I was able to develop my speaking skills by familiarizing the grammatical structures in the English Language.	3.07	Applicable
19. I gained so much confidence in speaking because I now know how to pronounce words and emphasize them to make the communicative effect of my speech more impactful.	3.24	Applicable
20. I have improved my comprehension in speaking.	3.22	Applicable
Average Weighted Mean	3.28	Applicable

Table 4 shows the result on the “Degree of Applicability of Blended Learning in Developing the Students’ English Language Skills in Terms of Reading with an average mean of 3.28 describe as “Applicable” specifying that the indicators listed were all agreed upon by the respondents as well as were implemented in the selected locale of the study. The students, in the local of the study, finds reading activities in blended learning engaging and interactive added to the beauty of its variations and flexibility.

Based on the given indicators, the statement “My vocabulary increased as I went through the different tasks in blended learning” got the highest weighted mean equivalent to 3.85 with an interpretation of “Highly Applicable”. This was an indication that most of the respondents were aware of the foregoing activities related to reading skills as it was being taught using a blended learning approach. It was followed by the statement “I gained knowledge on defining words I used in my arguments and ideas” with a weighted mean of 3.54 and a verbal interpretation of “Highly Applicable”. Of the 20 indicators listed, the statement “I was able to learn how to show that I am listening by using my body language and gestures to convey my attention” got the lowest weighted mean of 2.50 with a verbal interpretation of “Applicable”.

The foregoing findings and implications lend support to the study of Kintu et.al (2017), who mentioned that blended learning was among the innovations embraced by both teachers and students in the teaching-learning environment. Its innovative approach involved the use of technology in a combined face-to-face and online learning amidst its biggest challenge on the students' commitment as well as their parents and guardians at home to ensure effective learning through the use of technology. Moreover, Morris (2018) stated that Blended learning is progressively becoming a prospect for higher education students. It permitted the improvement of face-to-face interface between teachers and learners, using the internet or computer-based techniques. According also to Mantyla (2018) blended learning was the use of two or more presentation and distribution procedures for improving both the content and the learners' experience. Blended learning used different approaches, comprising print-based materials, instructor- led training, and web-based training, for example. In a positive mode, it can be assumed that blended learning had always occurred since the appearance of the first learning technologies, because teachers and learners had always attempted to find an active compromise between sessions necessitating these skills and more classical face-to-face teaching sessions. It also strengthens and maximizes guide and interactive reading activities beyond traditional means. As Djiwandono (2018), dynamic interactions are easily created in blended learning and it facilitates interactive learning experiences and promotes healthy and engaging interactions between learners to learners, learners to learning facilitators, and learners to learning materials and tools.

This represents the grade 9 students' level of writing proficiency as determined by an evaluation of the appropriate use of grammar, punctuation, and spelling in the modified and contextualized DepEd learning activity sheets (LAS)/materials as presented below.

Table 5. Degree of Applicability of Blended Learning in Developing the Students' English Language Skills in Terms of Writing.

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I was able to use new words I learned in my writing activities.	2.55	Applicable
2. I now know how to relate unfamiliar words with other unfamiliar words.	3.50	Highly Applicable
3. I am now confident in using different terms since I already have a wide range of vocabulary.	3.48	Applicable
4. I gained knowledge on how I can construct words in meaningful ways.	3.59	Highly Applicable
5. I can easily tell how words are derived from their origins.	3.57	Highly Applicable

6. I now have a greater knowledge on syntactic structures that helps me understand how words function in a sentence.	3.58	Highly Applicable
7. I learned how word order is used in communication to determine the relationship between different words.	3.46	Applicable
8. I gained knowledge on what appropriate punctuation to be used to signify pauses, intonation, and stress words.	3.22	Applicable
9. I was able to recognize proper tenses to signify whether a statement refers to the present, the past or the future by applying parameters to the verbs.	3.27	Applicable
10. I obtained familiarity with determiners which helps me form essential questions and statements.	3.35	Applicable
11. I now know how to use connectors which helps me “connect” phrases, words or clauses to one another.	3.40	Applicable
12. I am aware now on how to pay attention if someone is speaking by giving them my undivided attention and knowledge the message they are conveying.	3.00	Applicable
13. I can now provide feedback immediately to tell that I understand what was being said.	3.44	Applicable
14. I now know how to respond appropriately on what I listened to by being candid, open and honest in my responses.	3.26	Applicable
15. I learned how to remain focused on my writing by selecting the idea or topic suitably. Remaining focused on the idea, using details and information to further develop the piece of writing.	3.27	Applicable
16. I was able to obtain knowledge that writing must be presented in an organized manner for it to be effective and meaningful.	3.11	Applicable
17. I am now fully aware of my word choice that involves using the right words in my writing that will give clarity, evoke feelings, moods, likes and dislikes, and create a vivid picture in my reader’s mind.	3.05	Applicable
18. I gained confidence in my writing because of clear sentences that make sense. I construct sentences that help the flow of my writing smoothly to show how my ideas relate.	3.18	Applicable

19. I am now familiar with proper conventions in writing and the editing process which includes spelling, indention, punctuation, grammar, capitalization and paragraphing. When conventions are used accurately, they allow the reader to follow the text and gain meaning from it.	3.14	Applicable
Average Weighted Mean	3.29	Applicable

Table 5 shows the results on the Degree of Applicability of Blended Learning in Developing the Students' English Language Skills in Terms of Writing with an average mean of 3.29 (Applicable) specifying that the indicators listed were all agreed upon by the respondents as well as were implemented in the selected locale of the study. Students were able to see the beauty of scaffolding and guided writing in blended learning and their ability to check their own pace and progress at the same time. Based on the given indicators, the statement "I gained knowledge on how I can construct words in meaningful ways." got the highest weighted mean equivalent to 3.59 with an interpretation of "Highly Applicable". This was an indication that most of the respondents were aware about the foregoing activities related to writing skills being enhanced by the use of a blended learning approach. It was followed by the statement "I now have a greater knowledge on syntactic structures that helps me understand how words function in a sentence." with a weighted mean of 3.58 and a verbal interpretation of "Highly Applicable". Meanwhile, the statement "I can easily tell how words are derived from their origins." got a weighted mean of 3.57 with a verbal interpretation of "Highly Applicable". Of the 19 indicators listed, the statement "I was able to use new words I learned in my writing activities." got the lowest weighted mean of 2.55 with a verbal interpretation of "Applicable".

Blended learning, as with the real teaching-learning experiences that transpired at Dolores National High School, was a great help during the pandemic. Students find a flexible way of learning during the pandemic through blended learning. They find it non-threatening and they find it less stressful; thus, they were motivated to interact and learn as they see the learning style as brand new and innovative. It hooked their interest and it made them develop positive attitude towards independent and interactive learning brought by blended learning. This is supported by a study Aji et.al (2020) that revealed how students perceive blended learning during the pandemic beneficial. They find it enjoyable, motivating as it is flexible and interactive as well as it improves their ICT skills.

Brzoska (2020) points out students' independence in blended learning making them highly motivated and engaged than ever. It was also revealed that students use it as a motivation to see how they progress and the feedback they received from it. It helped them explore and gain confidence in doing learning tasks such as reading and writing tasks.

Ferlazzo (2020) also noted flexibility in blended learning as engaging and motivating for students. Like with our students in the locale of the study, they find it engaging to work and complete writing tasks not just for an hour as in a usual traditional classroom but they find it helpful to adjust flexible time periods allotted to them in blended learning. It helps them self-direct their writing and enhance it in their pace within the time allotted. Then, feedbacks are

given and they see their learning progress. This is where independent learning becomes motivating and not taxing for students.

Significant Difference Between the Socio-Demographic Profile and Degree of Applicability of Blended Learning Modality in Reading and Writing.

Table 6. Significant Difference Between the Socio-Demographic Profile and Degree of Applicability of Blended Learning Modality in Reading and Writing.

	p-value	Verbal Interpretation
Socio-Demographic Profile	.577	Not significant
Degree of Applicability	.468	Not significant

Table 6 shows the “Significant Difference Between the Socio-Demographic Profile and Degree of Applicability of Blended Learning Modality in Reading and Writing”. In terms of p-value, Socio- Demographic Profile had .577 while the Degree of Applicability earned .468. All factors have a verbal interpretation of “Not Significant”. It showed that students’ age, gender, and socio-economic status are not significant to the degree of applicability of blended learning in the teaching of reading and writing skills to students.

The success and adaptability of blended learning associated with learning achievement and skill development performance are not entirely affected by their socio- demographic profiles. As presented by Song et.al (2018), learning success, through blended learning, comes in terms of students’ satisfaction, outcomes, motivation, and knowledge building also greatly attributed to students’ effective time management. Collaboration, among other factors, was also perceived by students as important in building their satisfaction in learning according to Eom, Wen, and Ashhill (2018). Learning innovations brought about by the effective use of technology and students’ interaction with teachers and fellow students contributed much to their learning satisfaction and success of blended learning as perceived by both students and educators as supported in another study by Naaj et al. (2018).

Situating the use of blended learning during the pandemic and post-pandemic time, students find the confidence and motivation to self-direct and regulate their learning pace and progress. Orlov et.al (2020) stressed out that there was little evidence to connect demographic profiles of students as affecting their learning during the pandemic. For the case of the negative effects of the teaching-learning process during the pandemic, the study further presented that the experiences, innovations, and teaching strategies utilized by teachers and course pedagogies contribute to either the positive or negative impact of blended learning during the pandemic or even in the post-pandemic time.

Significantly, blended learning success in the Philippine setting transform students to become actively engaged in learning activities facilitated to them particularly in teaching and developing the reading and writing skills. It also heightens their positive attitudes towards the teaching and learning process as they are become empowered learners who interact well with

their teachers, fellow students, and the learning materials and tools despite the availability of gadgets, technological advancements, and internet connection in the Philippines.

In the teaching of English reading and writing skills, blended learning also offers a promising innovation in pandemic and post-pandemic era in the Philippines and around the globe. It offers a supplementary innovation from the traditional teaching styles. As Rahayu (2018) delineated, blended learning is an interestingly effective combination of the traditional styles of learning via face-to-face learning interactions provided and improvised technological tools to keep students actively involved and engaged in building up their knowledge, skills, and attitudes to optimize their transformation.

Students gain great autonomy and motivation in blended learning mixed with the development of their ICT skills considered as an edge for 21st century learners as Darong (2022) contends. This holds true with how the students in the conduct of our blended learning in Dolores National High School. Their motivation and engagement in the facilitated blended learning is not restricted by their age, gender, and economic status. As a result, their English competencies in reading and writing were significantly improved.

Blended learning, as an approved learning modality in the Department of Education (DepEd), is a combination of face-to-face learning with a mix of online or offline learning, modular, television or radio-based instructions to facilitate distance learning. It is a stride of DepEd to continue learning amidst the challenges brought by time like the disruption of the normal face-to-face classes due to the pandemic. It adheres to the goals and objectives set forth in the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP).

Now in the post-pandemic, it is still of significant use when the need arises for learning to continue amidst disruptions of classes brought by other concerns like typhoons or any other risk-related causes. It supports the Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM) of Learning that the Department moves to fully realize and implement.

CONCLUSION

Summary of Findings

The study aimed to determine the applicability of blended learning modality in reading and writing in Dolores National High School, Ormoc City. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions: What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of sex, age and socio-economic status, What is the reading and writing skills performance level of the respondents, What is the degree of applicability of blended learning in developing the reading and writing skills of the respondents, Is there a significant difference in the degree of applicability of blended learning modality among different socio-demographic profiles, reading and writing skills performance level of the respondents, and What can be proposed based on the result of the study.

To find answers to the foregoing questions, the researcher conducted a modified survey from the selected Grade 9 students from Dolores National High School using the descriptive

method of research with the questionnaire as the primary data-gathering instrument. The study used a simple random sampling technique since the information or the data needed in the study will be very much accessible and convenient for the researcher. Statistical treatments such as frequency, percentage and Chi-square were used to determine if there was a significant difference between the socio-demographic profile, degree of applicability, and strengths and weaknesses of blended learning. These statistical measures were used to achieve the objectives of the study and to determine whether the results of the study were dependable. Moreover, the researcher put together all the information or data gathered based on the series of tests conducted. In the end, a proposed recommendation was projected to further achieve the efficient and effective practices of blended learning even beyond the post-pandemic time.

Based on a percentage of 95% of the total responses, it is determined that most respondents are between the ages of 14 and 15. This indicates that the majority of grade 9 students fall within that age range. Additionally, it reveals that the total proportion for the 91 female respondents is 65.5%, vs 34.5% for the 48 male respondents. The researchers' respondents are mostly women, which makes for some excellent findings. Finally, 61.2% of the information from the socio-demographic profile pertains to households with monthly incomes of Php 21,000 or more. This shows that students from families that make this much money each month can meet all of their needs in proportion to their reading and writing skills. Reading skills have a mean of 90.705 and writing skills have a mean of 89.949 in both performance levels, which come under the Instructional level of the Phil- IRI Criteria. This suggests that the majority of participants were classified as learners in terms of reading and writing comprehension, implying that they would benefit from reading instruction. They are not, however, children who refuse or withdraw from reading and writing. They can read and write with some help. The mean of reading skills demonstrates that the respondents' reading and writing applicability is very applicable. Because the data show that the mean value is 3.28 and 3.29, respectively. This suggests there is no statistically significant relationship between socio-demographic profile and the degree of applicability of blended learning modality in reading and writing. One can learn in both disciplines regardless of his/her socio-demographic status in life.

Conclusion

When utilizing technology for teaching and learning, creative methods of instruction involve a successful blended learning environment. An analysis of the socio-demographic profile of the learner, including sex, age, and socioeconomic status, as well as the learning outcomes as determinants for effectiveness, can contribute to the planning of effective learning environments that include both face- to-face lessons and online aspects. Most of the student characteristics and blended learning design elements discussed in this study play a significant role in the efficacy of both. Although blended learning is still a relatively new idea in most educational institutions today, recent research tends to indicate that it can significantly improve the student experience if it is done "appropriately". This study's goal was to examine how using blended learning affected the ability of the respondents in both reading and writing. Thus, regardless of a learner's socioeconomic status, blended learning has been demonstrated to be beneficial in improving their reading and writing skills. In conclusion, it is imperative to incorporate blended learning into both reading and writing instruction. As a result, it is possible

to recommend this strategy to both educators and stakeholders to improve the delivery of language education.

Recommendations

From the presented conclusions, the following recommendations were hereby directed and forwarded:

1. Requirement for training first teachers on key stage 2 level and urging them to promote active learning in-class blended learning.
2. Modify their methods and approaches in teaching from traditional to hybrid based on students' genuine involvement, and encouragement and allow Students to use English in "real-life" scenarios such as emails, chatting, forums, and texting
3. Encouraged the use of electronic communication tools to facilitate communication between both parties.
4. Conduct further research

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